
AWARENESS AND USE OF SMART PHONE BY THE UNDER GRADUATE STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY OF SANGLI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

In recent times 10 years launched online learning platforms in worldwide. The smart phones have surpassed the significance in the educational field. This study investigates the nature of the use and the perceived effectiveness of the smart phones. Every one can't run an individual operation without a smart phone, he feels uneasy, as if something is missing or frightened of losing contact with friends and family. The study reveals the used intelligent devices and awareness of under graduate students in college environment. The study's objectives were met through the use of an online questionnaire. The results reveal that every respondent has a smartphone, and the most popular app among students is WhatsApp. According to the findings, respondents believe that they have difficulty solving study-related problems if Internet connectivity is unavailable. In addition, some respondents think that mobile phones distract them and impact their health. The findings of this study show that while mobile devices are beneficial for studying these days, they should be used with parental supervision.

Keywords: *Use of smart phone, Mobile Device, Online Learning, m-Learning*

Introduction:

An internet and Information and communication technology (ICT) services have partial nearly every part of human survival. It's more and more seen in how individuals educate and find out. Mobile phones are used in every achievable situation, including the classroom, both overtly and quietly, according to even an essential examination of today's university students. The device appears to be capable of contributing as mobile phone technology develops. Because of its multi-functionality and efficacy, m-learning (mobile learning) has become a popular learning approach to education, notably higher education, worldwide.

Mobile learning is still in its infancy, despite the considerable development and the promise of mobile devices. Using mobile technology and the internet, students may obtain their study materials anywhere and anytime. Academicians can utilize mobile devices and applications to improve knowledge sharing activities and provide new methods to connect with their campuses, course materials, students' records, and colleagues.

Use of Smart devices for Learning:

The learning has many avenues, and it is open to many platforms where the Students' attention increases. Smartphones

ensure autonomy to the students over their educational experience (Buck et al., 2013) and enable standard learning information and opportunities (Day&Erturk,2017).There are many apparent advantages, but the most striking feature is the handy or portable size and its use in the classroom and away from the school (Mokoena, 2012). This potential makes it advantageous than the traditional platform for learning and teaching, which was characterized by books and chalk/marker boards and is confined to the physical location of the classrooms.

Due to their adaptability and efficacy, smartphones are more and more used for education actions. In the various studies planned, the intelligent devices in the classroom are found to improve cooperation, engagement, and students' interest in course content and assignments and facilitate determining and summative assessment methods. As a result of integrating mobile devices into the classroom, students will have more opportunities to connect with the outside world, such as their families.

The lost tendency of looking for specifics in books and other sources has passed. Suppose students use cell phones in the classroom. In that case, they can speedily access the most up-to-date information about everything and everything, which boosts student passion and contribution in their studies. They will also have instant entrance to knowledge about emerging technology in their fields of interest, which they may share with other students through a smartphone. Even though lecturing is one method of imparting knowledge to pupils, it does not retain their attention for very long. As a result, this kind of information exchange will considerably assist pupils in broadening their knowledge.

The conventional perform of visiting the library and looking for books, topics, and subjects have been replaced by out-of-the-way access. Many textbooks lack the information that students oblige. In the same way that smartphones provide up-to-date information, library books cannot. Only if students have quick access to up-to-date, right information on everything can their knowledge enlarge. On their cell phones, they may also save digital textbooks in .docx, .pdf, and other formats, as well as e-books. In favor of smartphones, pen drives, external hard discs, and other data storage devices are being phased out.

Smartphones cause health problems, particularly for the ear, nervous system, and heart. Vibrations emanating from smart phones raise many health issues. The telecommunication signals influence the body to considerable extent. Smart phones are at the moment causing a great deal of interference, where their use warrants at any time. The over-dependence of smart phones by students during studies affects creativeness and learning as they engage with the phones most of the time. Intelligent smartphones may have cloning difficulties. Cloning is when someone steals a company's classification digit and uses them to make long-distance calls on the owner's report.

Review of Literature:

During the COVID-19 outbreak, students may benefit from mobile learning to cover the gaps in their education, which is evident from many studies. (Biswas, Roy, and Roy (2020)) By June 2020, teaching has started to depend on smartphones, and intelligent devices influence the world. Although many developed nations consider mobile to be positive, a few countries such as

Bangladesh underutilizes learning as a robust educational tool. This method of surveying 416 students from several Bangladeshi institutions was utilized to understand their perspectives on using mobile phones as a learning tool. This investigation shows that most university students are positive towards mobile learning.

Gomez (2020) linked students' academic performance and their usage of smart phones in secondary schools. For this reason, the author has conducted secondary exploitation of the Ministry of Education database for 2017, which contains information on 1,887,027 students from 7381 Spanish secondary schools. A multilevel correlation study is used as a method of analysis. The findings revealed a substantial link between centers and areas that permit mobile devices in education and academic achievement.

The influence of using smartphones on undergraduate students' academic performance at North-West University in South Africa was investigated by Ifeanyi (2020). This study used a quantitative research technique to collect data from 375 under-graduate students using questionnaires to assess the effect. Many undergraduate students use their smartphones to communicate with their peers and professors. It was also discovered that using smart phones diverts students' attention away from their academics in several ways. The findings also revealed how smartphone use affects kids' academic ability and growth.

Research by Adjei (2019) used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and included 294 participants. The study was conducted using a survey research approach using questionnaires. The study's main goals were to determine the perceived as effusing smart phone in

learning activities, the perceived usefulness of a smart phone in students' academic achievement, the effect of using a smart phone in students' learning activities, and the factors that inhibit the use of a smart phone as a learning tool.

In a study, Hossain (2019) determined how mobile phone usage affects academic performance among male and female students at Jahangirnagar University in Bangladesh. A face-to-face survey was done among 274 students from different departments of Jahangirnagar University in Bangladesh, including 159 male students and 115 female students ranging from second to the fourth year. Gender, age, and a connection with someone of the opposite sex all have a considerable favorable impact on pupils' academic achievement. However, marital status, time spent on the phone, and the detrimental effect of telephone and application use while studying negatively impact students' academic performance. On the other hand, the author believes that mobile phone manufacturers should consider how young people utilize their phones for educational purposes.

Similarly, in his study, Darko-Adjei (2019) used questionnaires to survey research. The study's main goals were to assess the perceived convenience of using a smartphone in learning activities, as well as the perceived utility of a smartphone to look at the impact of using a smartphone on pupils' academic performance to explore the variables that prevent students from using a smartphone as a learning aid and from using a smartphone in their learning activities. According to the research, cell phones were also an essential element of distance learning students' academic pursuits in Ghana. However, the analysis indicated some barriers to smartphone need, such as smartphones

freezing during critical learning instances, unstable internet connectivity, impinging calls during classroom hours, and smartphone screen and key sizes, which made the smartphone unpleasant to use for learning, particularly in compare is on to laptops.

Objectives of the Present Study:

Use and awareness of mobile, find out under graduate students in Sangli district of Maharashtra.

1. To determine which sorts of devices are used under graduate students in Sangli district to the learning method.
2. To find out which application is most used by under graduate students in Sangli district. To explore the use of mobile data per day by under graduate students in Sangli district. To find out the mobile device can

change the reading habits of the under graduate students in Sangli district.

Significance of Research Study:

The mobile phones have become as significant as a person's gloominess in current years. When a person does not have access to a mobile phone, he feels uneasy, as if something is missing or frightened of behind drop a line to with contacts and relatives. With the so several crucial compensation to mobile phones, it's important to examine the conclusions of mobile communiqué studies.

Methodology:

This study take a survey method, with data collected via an online survey. The study's objective interview was under graduate students in Sangli district, Maharashtra, India. The population of the study consisted of 170 students in total.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Talukawise basic information of respondents

Sr. No.	Taluka	Male	Female
1	Miraj	10	10
2	Tasgaon	11	13
3	Kavthe Mahankal	12	11
4	Jath	13	12
5	Vita	10	9
6	Atpadi	11	8
7	Kadegaon	9	8
8	Palus	10	13

Table 1 demonstrates that male respondents account for a higher

proportion of total respondents than female respondents.

Table 2: Types of devices used by under graduate students in Sangli district.

Cell Phone	Laptop	Tablet	PDA
68.8%	26%	5.2%	00%

Figure 2: Shows use of cell phones of under graduate students in Sangli district.

Table 2 and Figure 3 show that under graduate students in Sangli district have cell phones. Figure 3 similarly

reveals that 26% of students use a laptop. However, there are no students who use a PDA in this table.

Figure 4: Depicts there as on for utilizing a mobile device

Figure 4 depicts the reason for utilizing a mobile device, which reveals that 14% of respondents used a mobile device for the study. Respondents also use their mobile devices for social networking,

accessing study materials, playing games, and other activities. According to this data, just 1% of respondents in Sangli district utilize mobile devices for digital payments.

Figure 5 reveals that 85 percent of respondents use Whats App the most frequently, followed by 58 percent who use Instagram and Telegram 29%. Under

graduate students in Sangli district also use Research Gate for their research. Twenty-three percent of those polled also use Twitter.

Figure 6 demonstrates that most respondents believe that removing Internet access from the phone will make it challenging to solve study-related problems. Simultaneously, some respondents believe they cannot live

without the internet. According to this graph, respondents believe that life would be challenging and separated from the rest of the world if they did not have access to the internet.

Figure 7. According to this graph, students under graduate students in Sangli district utilized an average of 2GB of data each day. Figure 7 also shows that 19% of

respondents use more than 2GB of data per day, and 19% consume more than 4GB of data per day.

Figure 8. According to their responses, 51 percent of respondents have a good influence of using a mobile device, and they study more with the aid of a mobile device at the same time. Although

31% of respondents did not consider these arguments, 18% of respondents under graduate students in Sangli district believe that using a mobile device reduces study time.

Figure 9 shows that under graduate students in Sangli district believe that using a mobile device impacts their health, with 29 percent of respondents not sure about, while just 12 percent believe that

using a mobile device has no impact on their health. According to this figure, using a cellphone for excuses is harmful to one's health.

Figure 10 demonstrates that under graduate students in Sangli district believe that using a smart phone is distracting.

They are unable to concentrate on their studies. Only 3% of respondents are disagree with it.

Figure 11 shows that using an intelligent phone speed up the completion of study-related tasks. It is supported by 88

percent of those who answered. Only 11.8 percent of those polled disagree with it.

Conclusion:

The smartphone is a significant component of our lives these days since it allows us to do many activities such as study, shopping, play games, view movies, make phone or text calls, and make online payments to others. The current study is limited to tap the use pattern of intelligent phones by under graduate students in Sangli district. The study's findings reveal that respondents had either a good or negative attitude about the use of mobile devices. According to the study's findings, every respondent owns an intelligent machine, and it tends to impact the life of the students. But it is our primary role to orient the students to the right learning path.

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